

Syntheses, characterizations and structures of cadmium(II) and zinc(II) pseudohalide complexes containing pyridylpyrazole ligand

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Manuscript received online 27 July 2012, revised 10 August 2012, accepted 13 August 2012

Abstract : The details of syntheses, characterizations and structures of cadmium(II) and zinc(II) pseudohalide complexes of the types $[M(L)(NCS)_2]$, $[M(L)(N_3)]PF_6$, $[Zn(L)(NCO)]PF_6$ and $[Cd(L)(NCO)_2](PF_6)_2$ (1-6) [$M = Cd^{II}$ and Zn^{II} ; $L = N,N$ -bis(3,5-dimethylpyrazol-1-ylmethyl)aminomethylpyridine] are described. All the complexes are characterized using their spectroscopic and other physicochemical results. Crystal structures of $[Cd(L)(NCO)_2](PF_6)_2$ (3) and $[Zn(L)(N_3)]PF_6$ (5) have been solved by single crystal X-ray diffraction measurements. Each metal center in binuclear compound 3 has double NCO^- bridged distorted octahedral structure whereas in mononuclear compound 5 adopts a distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry.

Keywords : Mononuclear Zn^{II} , binuclear Cd^{II} , pyridylpyrazole, pseudohalides.

Introduction

Pyrazole containing tripodal ligands and their metal complexes have been an active area of research due to modeling the active sites in biologically important molecules and rich coordination chemistry¹⁻⁸. Such ligand systems are used in drug design and in herbicides and fungicides and also in the building of polynuclear complexes^{9,10}. Bivalent cadmium and zinc are involved in many biochemical reactions¹¹ and their complexes with nitrogen containing ligands have potential applications in the areas of catalysis, luminescent materials etc.¹²⁻¹⁴. Many zinc complexes are used as drug¹⁵. A large number of zinc and cadmium complexes with nitrogen containing heterocyclic ligand and pseudohalides are known in the literature¹⁶⁻²⁶. The ring size, number of hetero atoms and nature of the substituent in the heterocyclic ring significantly control the chemical and physical properties of the complexes²⁷.

We were interested to isolate and characterize new polynuclear cadmium(II) and zinc(II) complexes with pyridylpyrazole based ligand in combination with pseudohalides. Herein, we report on the syntheses, characterizations and structures of cadmium(II) and zinc(II) complexes using different pseudohalides (NCS^- , N_3^- and NCO^-) and N,N -bis(3,5-dimethylpyrazol-1-ylmethyl)aminomethylpyridine (L). Successfully, we have isolated

a series of complexes and characterized using the spectroscopic and other physicochemical results. Single crystal X-ray diffraction measurements show structural confirmation of the complexes $[Cd(L)(NCO)_2](PF_6)_2$ (3) and $[Zn(N_3)(L)]PF_6$ (5).

Results and discussion

General characterization :

The pseudohalide containing cadmium and zinc complexes of the type $[M(L)(NCS)_2]$, $[M(L)(N_3)]PF_6$, $[Zn(L)(NCO)]PF_6$ and $[Cd_2(L)_2(NCO)_2](PF_6)_2$, where $M = Cd^{II}$ and Zn^{II} and $L = N,N$ -bis(3,5-dimethylpyrazol-1-ylmethyl)aminomethylpyridine were obtained in good yield through one-pot reaction of a 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 mole ratio of the metal salt (perchlorate/acetate), ligand L, the pseudohalide (NCS^- , N_3^- and NCO^-) and counter anion PF_6^- (except for 1 and 4) in methanol. There was no change on the composition of the complexes 2, 3, 5, 6 even after addition of excess N_3^- or NCO^- in the reaction mixture. Except 3, all complexes are mononuclear. Conductance measurement shows complexes 1 and 4 are non electrolyte indicating both NCS^- are coordinated with the metal atom. The molar conductivity in CH_3CN solution of complexes 2, 5 and 6 ($> 120 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) and 3 ($245 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) are consistent with 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 electrolyte, respectively²⁸. The presence of counter an-

ion in the complexes have been confirmed by IR spectra and single crystal structure diffraction study of complexes **3** and **5**. The EI mass spectra measurement shows an intense peak at m/z 495 for complex **1** corresponds to $(C_{19}H_{24}N_7SCd)^+$, at m/z 480 for complex **2** corresponds to $(C_{18}H_{24}N_9Cd)^+$ of the cadmium(II) complexes and for zinc(II) complexes, an intense peak obtained at m/z 447 for complex **4** corresponds to $(C_{19}H_{24}N_7SZn)^+$, at m/z 432 for complex **5** corresponds to $(C_{18}H_{24}N_9Zn)^+$ and at m/z 432 for complex **6** corresponds to $(C_{19}H_{24}N_9OZn)^+$ ion. Complex **3** is binuclear and the crystal structure of $[Cd(L)(NCO)_2](PF_6)_2$ shows that two NCO^- ions bridge two cadmium(II) centers by adopting end-on coordination mode and both the cadmium have octahedral geometry with CdN_6 coordination environment. Similar mononuclear complexes with NCS^- and binuclear double NCO^- bridged nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes were reported with this ligand^{29,30}. Complex **5** has distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry with ZnN_5 coordination environment. Based on the microanalysis data in addition to the above data, we propose that complexes **1** and **4** have octahedral geometry, complexes **2**, **5** and **6** have distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry as they have similar IR pattern. All complexes are soluble in common organic solvents like ethanol, methanol, dichloromethane and acetonitrile etc. Due to unavailability of diffraction quality crystal, crystal structure of **1**, **2**, **4** and **6** could not be solved. The coordination of ligand L with zinc(II) and cadmium(II) ions were verified by the 1H NMR spectral studies. Analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of the free ligand display two intense characteristics bands at 1610 and 1590 cm^{-1} due to pyrazole $\nu(C=N) + \nu(C=C)$ and all the complexes show two strong characteristic bands at ~ 1605 and ~ 1550 cm^{-1} indicating coordination of ligand L to the cadmium and zinc. The intense broad band of hexafluorophosphate anion appears at normal frequency 844 cm^{-1} for complexes **2**, **3**, **5** and **6**. The sharp peak at 2100 cm^{-1} for $\nu(NCS^-)$ for complexes **1** and **4**, at 2070–2080 cm^{-1} for $\nu(N_3^-)$ for complexes **2** and **5** and at 2213–2230 cm^{-1} for $\nu(NCO^-)$ for complexes **3** and **6** indicating the coordination of pseudohalide with the cadmium and zinc complexes³¹. This was supported by the single crystal X-ray structure data of complexes **3** and **5**. All other bands of the ligand are also present in the complexes (Table 2).

Electronic, fluorescence and NMR spectra :

The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in the range of 250–550 nm in CH_3CN solution and no characteristic bands were obtained in the visible region. All the complexes as well as the ligand exhibit two intense bands in the region of 262 and 229 nm and the transitions are presumably due to intra-ligand $\pi-\pi^*$ and $n-\pi^*$ transitions. The photoluminescence properties of the ligand L and its complexes were studied at room temperature (298 K) in CH_3CN solution. Ligand L does not exhibit photoluminescence upon excitation at 262 nm as well as 229 nm. The emission energy of all the complexes in CH_3CN solution is very weak in the range of 340 to 370 nm at both 229 and 262 nm in the excitation

Table 1. Analytical data of the complexes

Sr. no.	Compd.	Elemental analyses (%) :			Conductivity Λ_M (CH_3CN) ($\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$)	MS (EI) : (m/z)
		Found (Calcd.)				
		C	H	N		
1.	$[Cd(L)(NCS)_2]$	43.20 (43.45)	4.32 (4.34)	20.23 (20.27)	25	495 $(C_{19}H_{24}N_7SC)^+$
2.	$[Cd(L)(N_3)]PF_6$	35.34 (34.65)	3.85 (3.85)	20.15 (20.21)	120	480 $(C_{18}H_{24}N_9Cd)^+$
3.	$[Cd_2L_2(NCO)_2](PF_6)_2$	36.40 (36.52)	3.85 (3.84)	15.75 (15.69)	245	-
4.	$[Zn(L)(SCN)_2]$	47.20 (47.48)	4.74 (4.75)	22.08 (22.16)	20	447 $(C_{19}H_{24}N_7SZn)^+$
5.	$[Zn(L)(N_3)]PF_6$	37.66 (37.47)	4.22 (4.16)	21.66 (21.86)	126	432 $(C_{18}H_{24}N_9Zn)^+$
6.	$[Zn(L)(NCO)]PF_6$	37.49 (37.37)	4.18 (4.16)	16.72 (16.86)	150	432 $(C_{19}H_{24}N_9OZn)^+$

Table 2. IR data (cm⁻¹) of complexes

Sr. no.	Compd.	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{C}) + \nu(\text{C}=\text{N})/$	$\nu(\text{NCO}^-)/(\text{N}_3^-)/$	$\nu(\text{PF}_6^-)$
		pyrazole	(NCS ⁻)	
1.	[Cd(L)(NCS) ₂]	1610s, 1550vs	2100vs	-
2.	[Cd(L)(N ₃)]PF ₆	1602s, 1553vs	2055vs	844
3.	[Cd ₂ L ₂ (NCO) ₂](PF ₆) ₂	1606s, 1554vs	2213vs	842
4.	[Zn(L)(SCN) ₂]	1612s, 1551vs	2100	-
5.	[Zn(L)(N ₃)]PF ₆	1608s, 1552vs	2080vs	844vs
6.	[Zn(L)(NCO)]PF ₆	1614s, 1550vs	2230vs	844vs

energy states. No emission originating from metal-centered excited states are expected for the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes, since they are difficult to oxidize or reduce due to their *d*¹⁰ configuration. Thus, the emission observed in the complexes is assigned to the (π - π^*) intraligand fluorescence.

The ¹H NMR spectra of complexes [Cd(L)(N₃)]PF₆ (2), [Zn(L)(SCN)₂] (4) and [Zn(L)(NCO)]PF₆ (6) were recorded in CDCl₃ solution. The assignment has been made on the basis of spin-spin interaction and compared with free ligand values. It has been observed that all protons are present in the complexes but suffer down field shift compared to the ligand (Table 3).

X-Ray crystallography :

X-Ray crystal data and refinement :

The crystallographic data and details of data collection and refinement of the compounds 3 and 5 are given in Table 4. Crystal of suitable size was selected and immersed in partone oil, then mounted on the tip of a glass fiber and cemented using epoxy resin. Intensity data for both the crystals was collected using Mo-K_α X-ray ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) radiation on a Bruker SMART APEX diffractometer equipped with CCD area detector at 293 K and 100 K for compounds 3 and 5, respectively. The data integration and reduction were processed with SAINT

software³². An empirical absorption correction was applied to the collected reflections with SADABS³³ software programs. The structure was solved by direct methods using SHELXTL³⁴ and refinement was based on *F*² by the full-matrix least-squares technique using the SHELXL-97 program package³⁵. The non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropically. The hydrogen atoms were fixed geometrically and refined using the riding model.

Crystal structure of 3 :

The molecular structure consists of dimeric cation [Cd(NCO)(L)]₂²⁺ and the atom-labeling scheme are shown in Fig. 1. Selected bond lengths and angles related to metal coordination sphere are given in Table 5. The structure shows that the two NCO⁻ ions are bridging two cadmium(II) centers in an end-on fashion through N-coordination. The ligand L is tetradentate which utilizes all potential donor atoms-pyridine nitrogen N(1), tertiary amine nitrogen N(2), and two pyrazole nitrogen atoms N(4) and N(6). The two cadmium atoms have equivalent coordination environment having four bonds in the equatorial plane and being bonded to two nitrogen atoms N(1), N(2) of the ligand L together with two nitrogen atoms N(7) and N(7a) from two cyanate ions and the two nitrogen atoms N(4) and N(6) of the ligand in the axial posi-

Table 3. ¹H NMR spectra of the complexes in CDCl₃

Compd.	C ¹² H,	C ¹¹ H,	C ⁶ H	C ⁷ H,	C ¹ H	C ² H,	C ³ H	C ⁴ H	C ⁹ H,
	C ¹⁸ H	C ¹⁷ H	(s)	C ¹³ H	(d)	C ³ H	(m)	(d)	C ¹⁵ H
Ligand	(s)	(s)		(s)		(m)			(s)
[Cd(L)(N ₃)]PF ₆	2.03	2.21	3.88	4.98	8.50	7.12	7.57	7.18	5.78
[Zn(L)(SCN) ₂]	2.37	2.52	4.35	4.95	9.04	7.58	8.03	-	6.06
[Zn(L)(NCO)]PF ₆	2.28	2.51	3.99	4.52	8.08	6.05	7.67	9.01	5.94
[Zn(L)(NCO)]PF ₆	2.20	2.23	3.94	4.98	8.08	7.54	-	7.99	6.04

s - Singlet; d - Doublet; m - Multiplet.

Table 4. Crystal data and structure refinements for complexes **3** and **5**

	Complex 3	Complex 5
Empirical formula	C ₃₈ H ₄₈ Cd ₂ F ₁₂ N ₁₄ O ₂ P ₂	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ F ₆ N ₉ PZn
Formula weight	1247.66	576.80
Temperature (K)	293(2)	100(2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71073	0.71073
Crystal system	Triclinic	Orthorhombic
Space group	<i>P</i> -1	<i>Pbca</i>
<i>a</i> (Å)	10.1019(10)	17.4952(11)
<i>b</i> (Å)	11.9950(12)	14.0882(9)
<i>c</i> (Å)	12.2293(11)	18.7841(12)
α (°)	115.369(9)	90
β (°)	91.390(8)	90
γ (°)	110.603(9)	90
Volume (Å ³)	1226.2(2)	4629.8(5)
<i>Z</i>	1	8
Density (mg/m ³)	1.687	1.655
Absorption coefficient (mm ⁻¹)	0.298	1.206
<i>F</i> (000)	624	2352
Crystal size (mm)	0.35 × 0.28 × 0.26	0.34 × 0.30 × 0.26
Theta range for data collection (°)	3.1743 to 29.048	2.15 to 27.99
Index ranges	-12 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 13, -14 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 15, -5 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 15	-21 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 20, -11 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 18, -23 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 24
Reflections collected	8247	22194
Independent reflections	5137 [<i>R</i> (int) = 0.0760]	5373 [<i>R</i> (int) = 0.0282]
Absorption correction	Semi-empirical from equivalents	Semi-empirical from equivalents
Max. and min. transmission	0.8726 and 0.6570	0.7446 and 0.6846
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on <i>F</i> ²	Full-matrix least-squares on <i>F</i> ²
Data/restraints/parameters	5137/0/316	5373/0/310
Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	0.993	1.055
Final <i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0760, <i>wR</i> 2 = 0.1452	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0709, <i>wR</i> 2 = 0.1982
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.1607, <i>wR</i> 2 = 0.2062	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0802, <i>wR</i> 2 = 0.2064
Largest diff. peak and hole (eÅ ⁻³)	0.931 and -0.345	1.611 and -0.839

Fig. 1. ORTEP diagram depicting the cationic part of the dimeric structure of complex **3** with atom numbering scheme (30% probability factor for the thermal ellipsoids).

Table 5. Bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (°) of complexes **3** and **5**

Bond length		Bond angle	
[Cd₂(L)₂(NCO)₂](PF₆)₂ (3):			
Cd(1)-N(1)	2.322(6)	N(7)-Cd(1)-N(6)	108.7(3)
Cd(1)-N(4)	2.425(6)	N(7)-Cd(1)-N(1)	106.5(3)
Cd(1)-N(2)	2.458(7)	N(6)-Cd(1)-N(1)	144.5(3)
Cd(1)-N(7a)	2.513(6)	N(6)-Cd(1)-N(4)	93.8(2)
Cd(1)-N(7)	2.237(8)	N(7)-Cd(1)-N(4)	161.6(2)
Cd(1)-N(6)	2.286(7)	N(7a)-Cd(1)-N(2)	177.78(19)
		N(1)-Cd(1)-N(7)	86.2(2)
[Zn(L)(N₃)]PF₆ (5):			
Zn-N(1)	2.062(4)	N(7)-Zn(1)-N(4)	107.05(17)
Zn-N(2)	2.377(3)	N(7)-Zn(1)-N(6)	105.09(16)
Zn-N(6)	2.057(3)	N(4)-Zn(1)-N(6)	113.42(14)
Zn-N(4)	2.026(4)	N(7)-Zn(1)-N(1)	102.14(19)

Table-5 (contd.)

Zn-N(7)	1.978(4)	N(4)-Zn(1)-N(1)	107.83(14)
		N(6)-Zn(1)-N(1)	119.95(13)
		N(7)-Zn(1)-N(2)	177.98(17)
		N(9)-N(8)-N(7)	176.9(5)

tions. Bond length from Cd(1) are 2.322 Å to N(1), 2.458 Å to N(2) in the tetradentate ligand and 2.237 Å to N(7) and 2.513 Å to N(7a) of the bridging cyanate anion. The axial bond length Cd(1)-N(4) (2.425 Å) is longer than Cd(1)-N(6) (2.286 Å). The NCO⁻ ion is nearly linear with N(7)-C(19)-O(1) angle of 175.3(16)°. The Cd...Cd distance is 3.4744(12) Å.

Crystal structure of 5 :

The molecular structure of the cation in [Zn(L)(N₃)]PF₆ and the atom-labeling scheme are shown in Fig. 2. Selected bond lengths and angles related to metal coordina-

Fig. 2. ORTEP diagram depicting the cationic part of the complex [Zn(L)(N₃)]PF₆ with atom numbering scheme (30% probability factor for the thermal ellipsoids).

tion sphere for the structure are given in Table 2. The structure shows it is a mononuclear complex with ZnN₅ coordination environment and zinc has distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry. Zinc atom is bonded to three nitrogen atoms – pyridine nitrogen N(1), pyrazole nitrogen N(6) and N(4) atoms in the trigonal plane and the azide nitrogen N(7) and tertiary amine nitrogen N(2), in the

axial position. The bond distances in the trigonal planes are Zn-N(1) (2.062(4) Å), Zn-N(6) (2.057 Å) and Zn-N(4) (2.026 Å) are equal to each other. The axial bond distance Zn-N(2) (2.377 Å) is greater than Zn-N(7) (2.026 Å). All the Zn-N distances are consistent with the other ZnN₅ coordinated mononuclear trigonal bipyramidal complex reported in the literature³⁶. The coordination geometry around Zn^{II} ion is distorted trigonal bipyramidal as is evidenced from the values of trigonality index, τ (τ for the complex is 0.96) defined as $\tau = [|\theta - \phi|/60]$, where θ and ϕ are the two largest coordination angles³⁷.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All chemicals and solvents were of analytical grade reagents. Zn(CH₃COO)₂·2H₂O, Cd(CH₃COO)₂·2H₂O, KSCN, NaN₃, NaNCO (Loba, India) and NH₄PF₆ (Aldrich) were of reagent grade and used as received. Zn(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O and Cd(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O were synthesized by treating ZnCO₃ and CdCO₃ with dilute HClO₄ acid solution, followed by slow evaporation of the solution over steam bath. Ligand *N,N*-bis(3,5-dimethylpyrazol-1-ylmethyl)aminomethylpyridine (L) has been synthesized by following the reported method²⁹. Solvents used for spectroscopic studies were purified following the standard procedures.

Instruments :

The infrared spectrum (4000–400 cm⁻¹) was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrometer RX1 spectrum using KBr pellets. Elemental analysis (C, H and N) were carried out using a Perkin-Elmer IA 2400 series elemental analyzer. UV-Vis spectra (900–190 nm) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer model Lambda 35 in acetonitrile solution. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AV-400 NMR instrument in CDCl₃. Solution conductivity were measured in CH₃CN solution using Equip-Tronics conductivity meter (model no. EQ-660A). Fluorescence spectra were recorded on JASCO FP-6300 spectrofluorometer. Mass spectrums were measured on Waters Micromax mass spectrum analyzer.

Syntheses of complexes :

[M(L)(NCS)₂] (M = Cd (1), Zn (4)) :

A methanol solution (10 ml) of ligand L (0.162 g, 0.5 mmol) was added to a methanol solution (10 ml) of

$M(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.5 mmol) slowly with stirring. To the resulting solution, an aqueous solution (2 ml) of KSCN (0.097 g, 1.0 mmol) was added with stirring and finally light yellow solution was stirred for 6 h. The solution was filtered and the filtrate was left to evaporate slowly. Light yellow compound was collected by filtration and washed with ether. Yield 55%.

$[\text{M}(\text{L})(\text{N}_3)]\text{PF}_6$ ($M = \text{Cd}$ (2), Zn (5)) :

A methanol solution (10 ml) of ligand L (0.324 g, 1 mmol) was added to a stirred solution of $\text{M}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 mmol) in methanol (15 ml). After 10 min, a methanol solution (15 ml) of sodium azide (0.065 g, 1 mmol) was added slowly to the resulting solution. Finally, an aqueous solution (2 ml) of NH_4PF_6 (0.164 g, 1 mmol) was added into the mixture and stirring was continued for another 3 h. The solution was filtered and the filtrate was left to evaporate slowly. Yield 60%.

$[\text{CdL}(\text{NCO})_2](\text{PF}_6)_2$ (3) :

To a methanol solution (10 ml) of $\text{Cd}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.266 g, 1.0 mmol), ligand L (0.324 g, 1.0 mmol) in methanol (10 ml) was added slowly with stirring. After 5 min, an aqueous solution (2 ml) of NaNCO (0.065 g, 1.0 mmol) was added to the resulting solution. Finally, an aqueous solution (2 ml) of NH_4PF_6 (0.164 g, 1.0 mmol) was added with stirring and light yellow solution was stirred for 24 h. The solution was filtered and the filtrate was left to evaporate slowly. It was possible to obtain diffraction quality crystal after 5 days. Yield. 0.250 g (40%).

$[\text{Zn}(\text{L})(\text{NCO})]\text{PF}_6$ (6) :

This complex was synthesized following the same procedure as described for complex 3 except $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was used instead of $\text{Cd}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Yield 60%.

Conclusion :

This paper describes the syntheses and characterizations of mononuclear complexes of $[\text{M}(\text{L})(\text{NCS})_2]$, $[\text{M}(\text{L})(\text{N}_3)]\text{PF}_6$, $[\text{Zn}(\text{L})(\text{NCO})]\text{PF}_6$ and binuclear NCO⁻ bridged complex $[\text{Cd}(\text{L})(\text{NCO})_2](\text{PF}_6)_2$ [$M = \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$ and Zn^{II} ; L = N,N-bis(3,5-dimethylpyrazol-1-ylmethyl)-aminomethylpyridine]. The complexes are characterized by different physicochemical methods. The single crystal X-ray structure of $[\text{Cd}(\text{L})(\text{NCO})_2](\text{PF}_6)_2$ complex shows

two NCO⁻ ions bridged with two cadmium centers by end-on coordination mode and the crystal structure of $[\text{Zn}(\text{L})(\text{N}_3)]\text{PF}_6$ complex shows it has distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry with ZnN_5 coordination environment.

Supplementary materials :

Crystallographic data for the structure have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC 834084 for compound 3 and CCDC 834083 for compound 5. Copies of this information can be obtained free of charge from the Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB12 1EW, UK (Fax : 44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the UGC (F.No. 39-720/2010(SR)), New Delhi. ZM acknowledges the support from the UGC for RFSMS fellowship. We thank Professor S. Bhattacharyya of Banaras Hindu University and Dr. E. Suresh of Central Salt and Marine Chemical Research Institute, Bhavnagar for X-ray data collection and Mr. Ashok K. Vishwakarma of The M. S. University of Baroda, India for helpful discussion.

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